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DOROTHEA

DOcker-based fRamework fOr gaTHERing nEtflow trAffic

Changelog

VERSION	DATE	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	27/02/2020	First draft
0.2	12/03/2020	Added attack simulation and deployment in Docker
0.3	18/03/2020	Lab 1 on Docker
0.4	27/03/2020	Attack distribution added
0.5	07/04/2020	Integrated both attackers and revised the document
0.6	11/06/2020	Added package sampling and new way to launch the lab

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INTRODUCTION

This document constitutes the memoir of the creation of two labs to generate NetFlow traffic.

The first laboratory is created to generate traffic that we could consider normal. This laboratory is within the SCAYLE foundation and uses various *scripts* that generate traffic similar to what a user could generate. Subsequently, this laboratory has been deployed in Docker containers to facilitate its distribution and scalability.

The second laboratory has been designed to be able to simulate and capture the traffic generated when carrying out different attacks, such as port scans or denials of service. This lab has been deployed, like the previous one, in Docker containers and allows emulating different types of attacks simply by copying the *script* and launching the containers.

The purpose is to obtain a set of data that we will later label as real traffic on the one hand and attacks on the other. Once this process is done we will have 2 *datasets*; one with flows generated with NetFlow and the other with flows generated with CICFlowMeter. The objective is to train machine learning models in order to detect attacks in both types of flows and to be able to evaluate which models have a higher detection rate for each of the generated flows.

In principle we will focus on port scans but, thanks to the flexibility of the laboratories, it is also possible to obtain data from any type of attack to be able to analyze and catalog it later.

On the one hand, the first laboratory, whose diagram is shown in figure 1, has a virtual *router* in which a sensor is installed that receives all the NetFlow traffic that passes through it and sends it to another machine where all the generated NetFlow flows are stored.

Figure 1: Laboratory scheme 1.

In particular, the *router* also saves network traffic in PCAP format with the help of the `tcpdump` tool. With these PCAP files and using the `CICFlowMeter` tool we will generate the other type of flow. Furthermore, the *router* has two network interfaces: one connected to the *router* in Leon, through which it has an Internet connection, and the other connected to a network in which two machines in charge of generate traffic considered normal through different *scripts*. Finally, it should be noted that the machine that stores the NetFlow flows is also connected to the `textit` router.

On the other hand, the second laboratory, whose scheme is shown in figure 2, is completely isolated with no Internet access, which is beneficial since it does not introduce noise into the traffic generated by the attacks. .

In this laboratory, both the *router* and the machine that acts as the data warehouse are the same as in the first laboratory, but in the interface that was previously connected to the *router* in Leon, there is now a connected machine that acts as an attacker. This machine is in charge of launching attacks on the computers connected to the other network interface of the *router*. In this way, all traffic must pass through the *router* and, therefore, the desired flows are generated. As in the previous lab, the *router* also saves the traffic in PCAP format which is then used to generate `CICFlowMeter` flows.

Figure 2: Laboratory scheme 2.

ARCHITECTURE

This section describes the architecture of the machines and the configuration of each one of them. It is important to bear in mind that in the most modern version of the laboratory, Docker containers are used and therefore the resource expenditure is lower.

Lab 1

The machines have the following specifications:

Router virtual:

- **RAM: 4GB**
- **Storage: 50GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Ubuntu Server 18.04.4 LTS**

NetFlow stream receiving machine:

- **RAM: 4GB**
- **Storage: 100GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Ubuntu Server 18.04.4 LTS**

Traffic generating machines (2 machines):

- **RAM: 2GB**
- **Storage: 30GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Linux Lite**

Lab 2

The machines have the following specifications:

Router virtual:

- **RAM: 4GB**
- **Storage: 50GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Ubuntu Server 18.04.4 LTS**

NetFlow stream receiving machine:

- **RAM: 4GB**
- **Storage: 100GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Ubuntu Server 18.04.4 LTS**

Attacking machine:

- **RAM: 4GB**
- **Storage: 50GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Ubuntu Desktop 18.04.3**

Attacked machines (several machines):

- **RAM: 2GB**
- **Storage: 30GB**
- **CPU: 1 core**
- **OS: Linux Lite**

DEPLOYMENT

Next, the machines that are common in both laboratories are exposed with their functionality and characteristics, also including the details of their installation. The specific machines for each laboratory are described at the end of this section.

Virtual Router

The virtual *router* is the main element in both labs since all traffic goes through it. It has two network interfaces and contains the sensor in charge of transforming traffic into NetFlow flows. In particular, the configuration of the network interfaces is the same for both laboratories, thus providing flexibility and scalability to the project, since if at any time another type of laboratory is considered, this machine can be reused.

Configuring the network interfaces

The machine configuration has two network interfaces: one global and one local. The global interface (**WAN**), with Internet access, is intended only for the laboratory that generates normal traffic while the local interface (**LAN**) is for the network of computers connected to the *router*.

Once the installation of the Ubuntu base system is complete, we must configure the two network interfaces that we are going to use. In this case, **enpos3** will be the WAN and **enpos8** the LAN.

To do this we open the network configuration file and modify its content as follows ¹:

```
sudo nano /etc/netplan/50-cloud-init.yaml
```

We configure the file in the following way:

```
# This file is generated from information provided by
# the datasource. Changes to it will not persist across an instance.
# To disable cloud-init's network configuration capabilities, write a
  ↪ file
# /etc/cloud/cloud.cfg.d/99-disable-network-config.cfg with the
  ↪ following:
# network: {config: disabled}
network:
  ethernets:
    enp0s3:
      dhcp4: true
    enp0s8:
      addresses:
        - 192.168.1.1/24
      dhcp4: false
      nameservers:
        addresses:
```

¹It is possible that in different versions of Ubuntu the name of this file changes.

```
- 8.8.8.8
- 8.8.4.4
search: []
version: 2
```

We save the configuration and apply the changes:

```
sudo netplan generate
sudo netplan apply
```

DHCP server installation and configuration

Now we are going to install a **DHCP** server so that we do not have to assign a static IP to each computer on the LAN. To do this, we install the following package:

```
sudo apt-get install isc-dhcp-server
```

Once we have it installed, we edit the file **/etc/default/isc-dhcp-server** assigning to the parameter "INTERFACESv4" the interface of the network **LAN**:

```
sudo nano /etc/default/isc-dhcp-server
```

```
INTERFACESv4="enp0s8"
```

The next step is to configure the **DHCP** server. We do this by editing the **/etc/dhcp/dhcpd.conf** file:

```
sudo nano /etc/dhcp/dhcpd.conf
```

We configure the **DHCP** server as follows:

```
option domain-name "netflow.com";
option domain-name-servers 8.8.8.8, 8.8.4.4;
default-lease-time 600;
max-lease-time 7200;
ddns-update-style none;
authoritative;
log-facility local7;
subnet 192.168.1.0 netmask 255.255.255.0 {
    range 192.168.1.101 192.168.1.200;
    option subnet-mask 255.255.255.0;
    option routers 192.168.1.1;
    option broadcast-address 192.168.1.255;
}
```

Once the server is configured, we apply the new configuration and enable the DHCP server so that boot to system startup:

```
sudo systemctl restart isc-dhcp-server
sudo systemctl enable isc-dhcp-server
```

Firewall configuration

The first step to configure the *firewall* is to enable **UFW**:

```
sudo ufw enable
```

The next step is to enable packet forwarding from the Internet to our **LAN** network. To do this we open the file **/etc/ufw/sysctl.conf**:

```
sudo nano /etc/ufw/sysctl.conf
```

Here we only have to uncomment the following line:

```
net/ipv4/ip_forward=1
```

In Ubuntu 18.04 the file **/etc/rc.local** no longer exists, therefore we have to create it. This file will be executed every time the machine is started:

```
sudo nano /etc/rc.local
```

We configure the file **/etc/rc.local** in the following way (each rule in **iptables** is commented to know what each one does):

```
#!/bin/bash
# /etc/rc.local
# Default policy to drop all incoming packets.
iptables -P INPUT DROP
iptables -P FORWARD DROP
# Accept incoming packets from localhost and the LAN interface.
iptables -A INPUT -i lo -j ACCEPT
iptables -A INPUT -i enp0s8 -j ACCEPT
# Accept incoming packets from the WAN if the router initiated the
  ↳ connection.
iptables -A INPUT -i enp0s3 -m conntrack \ --ctstate ESTABLISHED,RELATED
  ↳ -j ACCEPT
# Forward LAN packets to the WAN.
iptables -A FORWARD -i enp0s8 -o enp0s3 -j ACCEPT
# Forward WAN packets to the LAN if the LAN initiated the connection.
iptables -A FORWARD -i enp0s3 -o enp0s8 -m conntrack \ --ctstate
  ↳ ESTABLISHED,RELATED -j ACCEPT
# NAT traffic going out the WAN interface.
iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o enp0s3 -j MASQUERADE
# rc.local needs to exit with 0.
exit 0
```

This *script* allows you to route the traffic that arrives both from *localhost* and from the LAN network that we have created. In addition, we forward the received packets through the **LAN** network interface to the **WAN** network, so the *router* will be able to route all the packets to where they belong. This *script* must be executed at machine startup, so we must give it execution permissions:

```
sudo chmod 755 /etc/rc.local
```

Now we reboot the machine for the changes to take effect.

NetFlow Installation and Configuration

Once we have configured the packet routing, we are going to configure the *router* to be able to generate and export the traffic in NetFlow format using a sensor. To do this, the first thing we must do is download the GitHub project that we are going to install to then export the traffic in NetFlow:

```
git clone git://github.com/aabc/ipt-netflow.git ipt-netflow
cd ipt-netflow
```

Now we must prepare the *kernel* of the operating system. To do this, we execute the following:

```
sudo apt-get install module-assistant
sudo m-a prepare
```

Next, we prepare **iptables**. To do this, we must install the following:

```
sudo apt-get install iptables-dev pkg-config
```

With all of the above ready, we compile the module as follows:

```
~/ipt-netflow# ./configure
~/ipt-netflow# make all install
~/ipt-netflow# depmod
```

Once the module is compiled, we execute it by writing in the parameter “destination” the address **IP** and the **port** to which we want to send the generated NetFlow traffic.

Finally, we must direct all IPv4 traffic to the NetFlow module as follows:

```
iptables -I FORWARD -j NETFLOW
iptables -I INPUT -j NETFLOW
iptables -I OUTPUT -j NETFLOW
```

We start the NetFlow sensor as follows:

```
insmod ipt_NETFLOW.ko destination=192.168.1.104:2055 debug=1
```

To see the flow statistics as in the figure 3, we execute the following command:

```
cat /proc/net/stat/ipt_netflow
```

This way we would already have the module installed and configured to export the traffic in NetFlow. If you want to see the parameters with which the NetFlow sensor is running as in the figure 4, you must execute the following command:

```
sysctl net.netflow
```



```
rnet@router:~$ cat /proc/net/stat/ipt_netflow
ipt_NETFLOW 2.4-12-g1519063, srcversion C1575F08D1F669FB4C289A9; llist
Protocol version 5 (netflow)
Timeouts: active 1800s, inactive 15s. Maxflows 2000000
Flows: active 3 (peak 709 reached 0d9h56m ago), mem 986K, worker delay 25/250 [1..25] (64 ms, 0 us, 3:0 0 [cpu0]).
Hash: size 126166 (mem 985K), metric 1.00 [1.00, 1.00, 1.00]. InHash: 211 pkt, 19 K, InPDU 0, 0.
Rate: 0 bits/sec, 0 packets/sec; Avg 1 min: 169439 bps, 14 pps; 5 min: 577301 bps, 42 pps
cpu#      pps; <search found new [metric], trunc frag alloc maxflows>, traffic: <pkt, bytes>, drop: <pkt, bytes>
Total    0;      907 3305798 301456 [1.00],      0      0      0      0, traffic: 3607254, 3161 MB, drop: 0, 0 K
Export: Rate 0 bytes/s; Total 40161 pkts, 14 MB, 301453 flows; Errors 0 pkts; Traffic lost 0 pkts, 0 Kbytes, 0 flows.
sock0: 192.168.1.104:2055, sndbuf 212992, filled 1, peak 9217; err: sndbuf reached 0, connect 0, cberr 26, other 0
```

Figure 3: NetFlow flow statistics.

```
rnet@router:~$ sysctl net.netflow
net.netflow.active_timeout = 1800
net.netflow.debug = 1
net.netflow.destination = 192.168.1.104:2055
net.netflow.flush = 0
net.netflow.hashsize = 126166
net.netflow.inactive_timeout = 15
net.netflow.maxflows = 2000000
net.netflow.protocol = 5
net.netflow.refresh-rate = 20
net.netflow.scan-min = 1
net.netflow.sndbuf = 212992
net.netflow.timeout-rate = 30
```

Figure 4: NetFlow sensor parameters.

In the case of wanting to change any of these parameters, such as the destination IP, we do it as follows (this will be effective for all the parameters that are intended to be changed):

```
sudo net.netflow.destination = 192.168.1.102:2055
```

CICFlowMeter installation

CICFlowMeter is a tool that allows extracting characteristics of the network traffic captured by the sensor. To do this, it is first necessary to collect PCAPs from the traffic of our machine through the tcpdump tool. These PCAPs are subsequently analyzed with the CICFlowMeter tool that reports a CSV file for each PCAP analyzed.

It is important to bear in mind that in order to use CICFlowMeter it is necessary to have Java installed and, in addition, the libpcap-dev library, since it is not installed by default in Ubuntu. To install this library we execute the following command:

```
sudo apt-get install -y libpcap-dev
```

Machine receiving NetFlow flows

This machine stores all NetFlow traffic that passes through the virtual *router* so that it can later be exported to a CSV file.

Installation and use of flow-tools

Flow-tools is a set of utilities for sending, collecting, processing and analyzing NetFlow data. We install this tool on the machine that receives the NetFlow flows in order to collect and process the flows sent by the *router*.

We start by installing flow-tools using the following command:

```
sudo apt-get install flow-tools
```

We open the flow-tools configuration file:

```
sudo nano /etc/flow-tools/flow-capture.conf
```

We comment all the content of the file and add the following in the final line:

```
-w /var/log/flow -n 275 0/192.168.1.1/2055
```

The **-w** parameter specifies the directory where the files containing the NetFlow streams will be saved, **-n** indicates the number of files that will be saved each day, 0 means that you need to listen on all interfaces 192.168.1.1 refers to the IP that will send the NetFlow sensor data and 2055 the port that will send the NetFlow data.

We create the directory where the files will be saved:

```
sudo mkdir /var/log/flow
```

Now we restart the flow-capture service to apply the configuration changes:

```
sudo service flow-capture restart
```

We check if flow-capture is working by observing its status and if there are any services listening on port 2055, figures 5 and 6 respectively:

```
sudo service flow-capture status  
netstat -anpl | grep 2055
```

Errors and attempts to send data from the NetFlow sensor are written to the file **/var/log/syslog** and can be viewed as follows:

```
sudo less /var/log/syslog | grep flow
```

Finally, we allow all incoming UDP connections to port **2055** in order to receive data from the NetFlow sensor installed in the *router*:

```
sudo iptables -A INPUT -p udp --dport 2055 -j ACCEPT
```

```
netdata@netflow-data:~$ sudo service flow-capture status
[sudo] password for netdata:
● flow-capture.service - LSB: collects NetFlow data
   Loaded: loaded (/etc/init.d/flow-capture; generated)
   Active: active (running) since Fri 2020-02-21 12:47:59 CET; 1 weeks 5 days ago
     Docs: man:systemd-sysv-generator(8)
    Tasks: 1 (limit: 1109)
   CGroup: /system.slice/flow-capture.service
           └─4892 /usr/bin/flow-capture -w /var/log/flow -n 275 0/192.168.1.1/2055

feb 21 12:47:59 netflow-data systemd[1]: Starting LSB: collects NetFlow data...
feb 21 12:47:59 netflow-data flow-capture[4883]: Starting flow-capture: flow-capture.
feb 21 12:47:59 netflow-data systemd[1]: Started LSB: collects NetFlow data.
feb 21 12:47:59 netflow-data flow-capture[4892]: setsockopt(size=4194304)
feb 21 12:48:30 netflow-data flow-capture[4892]: New exporter: time=1582285710 src_ip=192.168.1.1 dst_ip=192.168.1.104 d_ver=1
```

Figure 5: Status of the flow-capture service.

```
netdata@netflow-data:~$ netstat -anpl | grep 2055
(Not all processes could be identified, non-owned process info
will not be shown, you would have to be root to see it all.)
udp        0      0 0.0.0.0:2055          0.0.0.0:*
```

Figure 6: Services listening on port 2055.

If we want to convert the received NetFlow data to CSV format, we can do it in the following way:

```
flow-cat <<file>> <<file>> | flow-export -f 2 > <<file-name>>.csv
```

If we only want to visualize the flows collected in a file, we can do it in the following way:

```
flow-cat <<file>> | flow-print
```

Laboratory 1 - Specific machines

Machines that generate real traffic

These machines have *scripts* that generate web, mail and SSH traffic. Thus, the dependencies that must be installed for the project to work are:

Installation with **pip**:

- paramiko
- selenium
- xvfbwrapper

Installation with **apt-get**:

- xvfb

You also have to download the executable **geckodriver** from the following link: <https://github.com/mozilla/geckodriver/releases>. Once downloaded, we unzip it and then place the executable in the **/opt/** directory.

The project runs on **Python 2.7** and is divided into four subfolders:

- **browsing: Generate real web traffic.**

It is launched by executing the file **browsing.py** and a parameter, which must be " p " to simulate a user looking for private things and any other parameter to simulate searches related to the job.

- **mailing: Generate SMTP or email traffic.**

It is launched by running the **mailing.py** file. You have to configure the **mail.ini** file with the email address, the password and the SMTP server we want to connect to (in the case of Gmail the server is **smtp.gmail.com**).

- **ssh: Generate SSH traffic.**

It is launched by executing the file **sshtraffic.py** and within the *script* you have to configure the IP address to which we want to connect, the username and the password.

- **system: Saves the logs of the scripts.**

It is launched by running the file **printLog.py**.

The project is launched from a single *script*, **generate-traffic.py**, in charge of launching each of the previous files to generate traffic with an interval 5 minutes apart between them.

Code 1: generate-traffic.py

```
import browsing.browsing as br
import mailing.mailing as mail
import ssh.sshtraffic as traffic
import system.printLog as log
import time
import os

sshportlist = [22,80,443,636,3389]

while 1:
    #We simulate doing internet searches
    br.main('p')
    log.echoC("User", "I take a break")
    time.sleep(20)
    log.echoC("User", "I'm back from the break")
    os.system("killall firefox 2> /dev/null")

    #We simulate a user who sends emails
    mail.main()
    log.echoC("User", "I take a break")
        time.sleep(20)
        log.echoC("User", "I'm back from the break")

    #We simulate connecting to a machine by ssh
    for each in sshportlist:
        traffic.main(each)

        log.echoC("User", "I take a break")
```

```
time.sleep(20)
log.echoC("User", "I'm back from the break")
```

In addition, we create the *script* **start_generate_traffic.sh** so that the project is constantly running:

```
# nano /home/debusr/start_generate_traffic.sh
```

Code 2: start_generate_traffic.sh

```
#!/bin/bash
number="$(ps -aux | grep '/usr/bin/python /generate-traffic/generate-traffic.py' | wc -l)"
if [ "$number" -ge "2" ]
then
echo "generate traffic is running"
else
echo "generate traffic stopped"
/usr/bin/python /generate-traffic/generate-traffic.py 2> /dev/null &
fi
```

Next we put the *script* in the crontab so that it runs every 2 minutes, thus checking that the project is launched and, failing that, it launches it:

```
# crontab -e -u debusr
```

```
# m h dom mon dow command
*/2 * * * * /home/debusr/start_generate_traffic.sh > /dev/null
```

Laboratory 2 - Specific machines

Attacking machine

The attacking machine is in charge of launching the port scan attacks against the machines that have been created in the other local network.

In the attacks the attacker's IP is random, then when building the *dataset* the attacks shown are not always carried out from the same IP.

In particular, the option of capturing the packets and modifying the IP from which the attacks are launched was valued, but it was discarded since when modifying that IP, the response of the attacked computers would not reach the attacking machine and that information would be lost.

In a second version of the lab, explained at the end of this document, distributed attacks have been implemented from different machines executing the same attack *script* thanks to the use of queues.

The port scan attacks have been automated with the following *script*:

```
import nmap
import os
import random
```



```
import time

NUMERO_PUERTOS = 65536

# Creamos las variables de los puertos que utilizaremos para escanear
↳ todo el rango.

class Generador_Atques():

    def __init__(self):
        pass

    def realizar_ataques(self):
        puertoActual = 1
        numeroEscaneos = 9
        intervaloPuertos = 1024
        arrayArgumentos = ['-sU', '-sO', '-sM', '-sN', '-sF', '-sS', '-sT', '-sA',
            ↳ -sW', '-sX']
        puertoSiguiente = intervaloPuertos
        # Imprimimos la hora de inicio del ataque.
        print('Inicio del ataque: ' + time.strftime("%H:%M:%S"))
        # Con esto conseguimos que se aleatorice tanto el puerto de origen
        ↳ como la IP de origen.
        while puertoSiguiente < NUMERO_PUERTOS or numeroEscaneos != 0:
            nm = nmap.PortScanner()
            results = nm.scan(self.aleatorizar_ips(), str(puertoActual) + '-' + str
                ↳ (puertoSiguiente), arguments=arrayArgumentos[numeroEscaneos])

            #print(results)
            #print('\n\n')
            # Una vez completados todos los puertos, cambiamos de ataque y
            ↳ actualizamos los contadores.
            if puertoSiguiente == NUMERO_PUERTOS:
                numeroEscaneos = numeroEscaneos - 1
                puertoActual = 1
                puertoSiguiente = 1024
                self.cambiar_interfaz_red()
                # Actualizamos los puertos a escanear.
                puertoActual = puertoSiguiente
                puertoSiguiente = puertoSiguiente + intervaloPuertos
            # Hora de fin.
            print('Fin del ataque: ' + time.strftime("%H:%M:%S"))

    def cambiar_interfaz_red(self):
        # Generamos un numero aleatorio entre 2 y 255 que sera el ultimo valor
        ↳ de la IP.
        randIP = random.randrange(2, 255)
        print(randIP)
```



```
# Cambiamos la IP de la maquina en el archivo de configuracion de red
↳ y aplicamos los cambios.
os.system('sed -i \'/addresses/c\ \addresses: [10.10.10.' + str(randIP
↳ ) + '/24]\' /etc/netplan/01-network-manager-all.yaml')
os.system('netplan generate')
os.system('netplan apply')

def aleatorizar_ips(self):
    randIP = random.randrange(100,104)
    ip = "192.168.1." + str(randIP)
    #ip = "192.168.1.103"
    return ip

atacar = Generador_Atques()
atacar.cambiar_interfaz_red()
atacar.realizar_ataques()
```

LABORATORY CONTAINERIZATION

Once the laboratories have been deployed on physical machines, and with the intention of facilitating their distribution and scalability, they have been containerized in Docker. Thanks to this process, being able to replicate the work done means launching a single command that raises the laboratories, thus allowing any experiment to be scaled. Without going any further, and for example, Docker allows us to raise 100 attackers within the same team to distribute an attack *script*.

The figure 7 shows the general structure, where each folder corresponds to the respective laboratory (one to carry out the attacks and the other to generate traffic classified as normal).

Figure 7: Structure of the laboratories.

In particular, the configuration of the laboratories is carried out in the file **config.yaml**.

Code 3: config.yaml

```
lab_attacks:
  attackers: 100
  slaves: 200
  sampling:
    enabled: true
    packet_sampling: 1000
  networks:
    internal_net: 152.148.48.0
    attacker_net: 140.30.20.0

lab_normal:
  generators: 3
  mailing:
    username: test@test.com
    password: 12345
    smtp: smtp.gmail.com
  sampling:
    enabled: true
    packet_sampling: 500
  networks:
    internal_net: 182.168.1.0
    internet: 126.52.30.0
```

Also, the lab is launched using the **run.py** file as follows:

- If you want to launch the attack laboratory, you must choose the option **-t attack**:

```
sudo python3 run.py -t attack
```

- If, on the other hand, you want to launch the laboratory to generate normal traffic, you must choose the **-t normal** option:

```
sudo python3 run.py -t normal
```

- Additionally, if you want to delete the containers and images of the laboratory that have been created previously, you have the option **-c**:

```
sudo python3 run.py -c
```

Code 4: run.py

```
import os
import argparse
import yaml
from joblib import dump, load
import sys
import signal

parser = argparse.ArgumentParser()
parser.add_argument("-t", "--type", help="attack or normal type")
parser.add_argument("-c", "--clean", nargs='?', const='clean', help="clean
↳ all struct")
args = parser.parse_args()
signal.signal(signal.SIGINT, signal.SIG_IGN)

if os.geteuid() != 0:
    print('You must have root privileges for this script.')
    sys.exit(1)

if not args.type:
    print("a type is required")
    parser.print_help()
    quit()

#We read the configuration file
with open("config.yaml") as f:
    conf_file = yaml.load(f, Loader=yaml.FullLoader)
f.close()

if args.clean:

    os.system('docker rm $(docker ps -a -q)')
    os.system('docker rmi $(docker images -q)')
if args.type == 'attack':
```

```
#Delete the kernel module
os.system('sudo rmmod ipt_NETFLOW 2> /dev/null')

attackers = conf_file["lab_attacks"]["attackers"]
slaves = conf_file["lab_attacks"]["slaves"]

# Change slaves.
os.system('sed -i `'/slaves = /c\\\tslaves = '+ str(slaves) +'\`' ./
↳ lab_attacks/attacks/tasks.py')

#We change the sampling
if conf_file["lab_attacks"]["sampling"]["enabled"] == True:
    sampling = conf_file["lab_attacks"]["sampling"]["packet_sampling"]
else:
    sampling = 1
os.system('sed -i `'/sampling=/c\\\sampling='+str(sampling)+'\`' ./
↳ lab_attacks/router/start.sh')

#change ips
with open("lab_attacks/docker-compose.yml") as f:
    conf_file_compose = yaml.load(f, Loader=yaml.FullLoader)
    attacknet_old = conf_file_compose["networks"]["attacknet"]["ipam"]["
↳ config"]
    internal_net_old = conf_file_compose["networks"]["internalnet"]["
↳ ipam"]["config"]
f.close()

internal_new = conf_file["lab_attacks"]["networks"]["internal_net"]
attacknet_new = conf_file["lab_attacks"]["networks"]["attacker_net"]
os.system('find ./lab_attacks/ -name "*" -print | xargs sed -i "s/'
↳ + attacknet_old[0]["gateway"][: -2] + '/' + attacknet_new[: -2] + '/'g"
↳ ')
os.system('find ./lab_attacks/ -name "*" -print | xargs sed -i "s/'
↳ + internal_net_old[0]["gateway"][: -2] + '/' + internal_new[: -2] + '/'g
↳ "')

os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_attacks/docker-compose.yml build')
os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_attacks/docker-compose.yml up --
↳ scale attacker='+str(attackers)+' --scale slave='+str(slaves)+'
↳ --force-recreate --abort-on-container-exit')
```

```
if args.type == 'normal':
    os.system('sudo rmmod ipt_NETFLOW 2> /dev/null')
```



```
generators = conf_file["lab_normal"]["generators"]
if conf_file["lab_normal"]["sampling"]["enabled"] == True:
    sampling = conf_file["lab_normal"]["sampling"]["packet_sampling"]
else:
    sampling = 1

#We change the sampling
os.system('sed -i \'/sampling=/c\\sampling='+str(sampling)+'\' ./
↳ lab_normal/router/start.sh')

#Change mail config

user = conf_file["lab_normal"]["mailing"]["username"]
pw = conf_file["lab_normal"]["mailing"]["password"]
smtp = conf_file["lab_normal"]["mailing"]["smtp"]

os.system('sed -i \'/user =/c\\user = '+str(user)+'\' ./lab_normal/
↳ generator/generate-traffic/mailing/mail.ini')
os.system('sed -i \'/pw/c\\pw = '+str(pw)+'\' ./lab_normal/generator/
↳ generate-traffic/mailing/mail.ini')
os.system('sed -i \'/smtp/c\\smtp = '+str(smtp)+'\' ./lab_normal/
↳ generator/generate-traffic/mailing/mail.ini')

#change ips
with open("lab_normal/docker-compose.yml") as f:
    conf_file_compose = yaml.load(f, Loader=yaml.FullLoader)
    internet_old = conf_file_compose["networks"]["internet"]["ipam"]["
↳ config"]
    internal_net_old = conf_file_compose["networks"]["internalnet"]["
↳ ipam"]["config"]
f.close()

internal_new = conf_file["lab_normal"]["networks"]["internal_net"]
internet_new = conf_file["lab_normal"]["networks"]["internet"]
os.system('find ./lab_normal/ -name "*" -print | xargs sed -i "s/' +
↳ internet_old[0]["gateway"][:-2] + '/' + internet_new[:-2] + '/g"')
os.system('find ./lab_normal/ -name "*" -print | xargs sed -i "s/' +
↳ internal_net_old[0]["gateway"][:-2] + '/' + internal_new[:-2] + '/g"
↳ ')
os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_normal/docker-compose.yml build')
os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_normal/docker-compose.yml up --
↳ scale generator='+str(generators)+' --force-recreate -d')

while True:
    print('Press any key to see the flowNumbers, write save to end the
↳ lab')
```

```
fin = input()
if fin == "save":
    print('Saving data, wait please')
    os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_normal/docker-compose.yml exec
    ↪ router ./getCIC.sh ')
    os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_normal/docker-compose.yml down'
    ↪ )
    print('data stored, BYE!!!!!!')
    break
else:
    os.system('docker-compose -f ./lab_normal/docker-compose.yml exec
    ↪ netflow_warehouse ./checkFlows.sh')
```

Lab 1 - Docker

In this laboratory, Docker Compose has been used to generate real traffic, so that the infrastructure is exportable and lighter to mount.

In the file **docker-compose.yml** we define the machines and networks that we are using. On the one hand, we define a network for the *router* to connect to the Internet and, on the other hand, the network where the stream store is located, the machine that receives the sampled network traffic and the machines that generate the traffic real. In this way, the resulting folder structure is the one presented in figure 8.

Figure 8: Laboratory structure 1.

Code 5: docker-compose.yml

```
version: "2"
services:

  netflow_warehouse:
    image: lab/netflow_warehouse
    build: ./netflow_warehouse
    container_name: netflow_warehouse_normal
    volumes:
      - ./results/netflow-flows:/home/netflow_flows
    networks:
      internalnet:
        ipv4_address: 182.168.1.4
    depends_on:
```

```
- router
privileged: true
tty: true

ssh:
  image: lab/ssh
  build: ./ssh
  container_name: ssh_normal
  networks:
    internalnet:
      ipv4_address: 182.168.1.9
  depends_on:
    - router
    - netflow_warehouse
  privileged: true
  tty: true

router:
  build: ./router
  image: lab/router
  container_name: router_normal
  volumes:
    - ./results/network-traffic:/home/total-traffic/
    - ./results/CICFlows:/home/cic-total/
  networks:
    internet:
      ipv4_address: 126.52.30.2
    internalnet:
      ipv4_address: 182.168.1.2
  privileged: true
  tty: true

netflow_generator:
  container_name: netflow_generator_normal
  build: ./netflow_generator
  image: lab/netflow_generator
  volumes:
    - ./results/NetflowMachineResults:/home/total-traffic/
  networks:
    internalnet:
      ipv4_address: 182.168.1.3
  privileged: true
  tty: true

generator:
```

```
build: ./generator
image: lab/generator
depends_on:
  - router
  - netflow_warehouse
networks:
  - internalnet
privileged: true
tty: true
```

```
networks:
  internet:
    driver: bridge
    ipam:
      config:
        - subnet: 126.52.30.0/24
          gateway: 126.52.30.1

  internalnet:
    driver: bridge
    ipam:
      config:
        - subnet: 182.168.1.0/24
          gateway: 182.168.1.1
```

Dockerfile router

We install Java and copy the CICFlowMeter tool to generate flows through PCAPs that we will obtain with the tcpdump tool that is running in this container **Dockerfile**.

Code 6: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04

#Install the necessary packages
RUN apt-get -y update;
RUN apt-get -y install net-tools
RUN apt-get -y install apt-utils
RUN apt-get -y install iputils-ping nano tcpdump
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y python3.6
RUN apt-get install -y python3-pip
RUN pip3 install pandas

# Enable forwarding
RUN sysctl net.ipv4.conf.all.forwarding=1
```

```
# Install and configure the Netflow sensor
RUN apt-get -y install git
RUN apt-get -y install module-assistant
RUN apt-get -y install build-essential
RUN apt-get -y install iptables iptables-dev pkg-config
RUN DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive /usr/bin/apt-get install -y -q --
    ↪ allow-change-held-packages linux-image-$(uname -r)
RUN apt-get -y install linux-headers-$(uname -r)
RUN apt-get -y install cron

#Install java to be able to use CICFlowMeter
RUN apt-get install -y openjdk-8-jdk

#Install mergecap included in Wireshark and libcap since CIC needs this
    ↪ dependency
RUN DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive apt-get install -y wireshark-common
RUN apt-get install -y libcap-dev

#Clone the project that emulates a router with netflow
RUN git clone git://github.com/aabc/ipt-netflow.git ipt-netflow;
RUN mkdir /home/CICFlowMeter40
COPY ./CICFlowMeter40/ /home/CICFlowMeter40

#Install ssh server
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y openssh-server
RUN apt-get install sshpass
RUN mkdir /var/run/sshd
RUN echo 'root:password' | chpasswd
RUN sed -i 's/#PermitRootLogin prohibit-password/PermitRootLogin yes/' /
    ↪ etc/ssh/sshd_config

# SSH login fix. Otherwise user is kicked off after login
RUN sed 's@session\s*required\s*pam_loginuid.so@session optional
    ↪ pam_loginuid.so@g' -i /etc/pam.d/sshd
ENV NOTVISIBLE "in users profile"
RUN echo "export VISIBLE=now" >> /etc/profile
EXPOSE 22

#Check if the attacks have been carried out and if so we save the
    ↪ results
WORKDIR /
RUN echo 0 > checkRouter.txt
RUN echo 0 > checkRouterNetflow.txt

COPY getCIC.sh .
COPY clean-CIC.py .

RUN chmod +x getCIC.sh
```

```
RUN chmod +x /home/CICFlowMeter40/bin/cfm

#Create the directories to store the traffic generated by tcp-dump
RUN mkdir /home/tcpdump-captures
RUN mkdir /home/total-traffic
RUN mkdir /home/cic-flows
RUN mkdir /home/total-cic

#Launch start.sh
COPY start.sh .
RUN chmod +x start.sh
CMD ["/start.sh"]
```

Inside the container we have the *script* **getCIC.sh** that exports the NetFlow traffic flows captured with tcpdump in CSV format, saves them in our *host* and close the lab.

Code 7: getCIC.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

#We transform the flows stored in the router in a csv
mergcap -w /home/total-traffic/merged.pcap /home/tcpdump-captures/*

cd /home/CICFlowMeter40/bin/
#We generate the CICFlowMEter of each pcap
./cfm /home/tcpdump-captures/ /home/cic-flows/

cat /home/cic-flows/*.csv > /home/cic-total/cic-merged.csv

python3 /clean-CIC.py

#We instruct the receiver to export the captured netflow flows
sshpass -p "password" ssh -o StrictHostKeyChecking=no root@182.168.1.4
↪ "echo 1 > /checkReceiver.txt"
sshpass -p "password" ssh -o StrictHostKeyChecking=no root@182.168.1.3
↪ "echo 1 > /checkNetflow.txt"

#We wait for the receiver to finish
while true;

do

var=$(cat /checkRouter.txt)
var2=$(cat /checkRouterNetflow.txt)

if [ $var -eq 2 ] && [ $var2 -eq 2 ];then
break;
else
sleep 20
```


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fi
done

Code 8: clean-CIC.py

```
import pandas as pd

dataset = pd.read_csv("/home/cic-total/cic-merged.csv")
index = dataset.loc[(dataset['Flow ID'] == 'Flow ID')].index.values.
    ↪ astype(int)
dataset = dataset.drop(index)

dataset.to_csv("/home/cic-total/cic-merged.csv", index=False, encoding='
    ↪ utf-8-sig')
```

We will need to sample network traffic, that is, 1 out of every X packets is scanned. To do this, in the *script* **start.sh** that is executed when starting the container, using **iptables** rules, take 1 of each X packages, and we send it to the machine named `textbf netflow_generator`, which will be in charge of receiving the sampled traffic and converting it into NetFlow.

Code 9: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash
sampling=500
iptables -t mangle -A PREROUTING -m statistic --mode nth --every
    ↪ $sampling --packet 0 -j TEE --gateway 182.168.1.3

#We indicate the default gateway is that of the WAN network, through
    ↪ which it goes to the internet
route add default gw 126.52.30.1
route del default gw 182.168.1.1

#We indicate that NAT traffic goes to the Internet
iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o eth1 -j MASQUERADE

/etc/init.d/ssh start

#We launch tcp-dump storing the packages every 20 mb
tcpdump -i eth0 -C 1 -w '/home/tcpdump-captures/capture.pcap'
```

To save the generated flows and close the laboratory we will only have to write the word **save**. The flows generated, both from CICFlowMeter and NetFlow, and the traffic captured by tcpdump, in addition to the traffic sampled, will be saved in the **results** folder, the content of which is exposed in the figure 9.

Figure 9: Lab 1 “results” folder.

Dockerfile netflow_generator

This container **Dockerfile** is in charge of receiving the sampled traffic and generating the NetFlow flows. Once generated, it sends them to the **netflow_warehouse**, where they are stored.

Code 10: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04

#Install the necessary packages
RUN apt-get -y update;
RUN apt-get -y install net-tools
RUN apt-get -y install apt-utils
RUN apt-get -y install iputils-ping nano tcpdump
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y python3.6
RUN apt-get install -y python3-pip
RUN pip3 install pandas

# Enable forwarding
RUN sysctl net.ipv4.conf.all.forwarding=1

# Install and configure the Netflow sensor
RUN apt-get -y install git
RUN apt-get -y install module-assistant
RUN apt-get -y install build-essential
RUN apt-get -y install iptables iptables-dev pkg-config
RUN DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive /usr/bin/apt-get install -y -q --
    ↪ allow-change-held-packages linux-image-$(uname -r)
RUN apt-get -y install linux-headers-$(uname -r)
RUN apt-get -y install cron

#Install mergecap included in Wireshark and libcap since CIC needs this
    ↪ dependency
RUN DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive apt-get install -y wireshark-common
RUN apt-get install -y libpcap-dev

#Clone the project that emulates a router with netflow
RUN git clone git://github.com/aabc/ipt-netflow.git ipt-netflow;

#Create the results folder
RUN mkdir /home/netflow_flows

#Launch the project
WORKDIR /ipt-netflow
RUN ./configure
RUN make all install
RUN depmod
```

```
#Install ssh server
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y openssh-server
RUN apt-get install sshpass
RUN mkdir /var/run/sshd
RUN echo 'root:password' | chpasswd
RUN sed -i 's/#PermitRootLogin prohibit-password/PermitRootLogin yes/' /
↳ etc/ssh/sshd_config

# SSH login fix. Otherwise user is kicked off after login
RUN sed 's@session\s*required\s*pam_loginuid.so@session optional
↳ pam_loginuid.so@g' -i /etc/pam.d/sshd
ENV NOTVISIBLE "in users profile"
RUN echo "export VISIBLE=now" >> /etc/profile
EXPOSE 22

#Check if the attacks have been carried out and if so we save the
↳ results
WORKDIR /

COPY CIC-cron /etc/cron.d/CIC-cron
RUN chmod 0644 /etc/cron.d/CIC-cron
RUN crontab /etc/cron.d/CIC-cron
RUN touch /var/log/cron.log

RUN mkdir /home/tcpdump-capture/
RUN mkdir /home/total-traffic/

RUN echo 0 > checkNetflow.txt
COPY get-data.sh .
RUN chmod +x get-data.sh

#Launch start.sh
COPY start.sh .
RUN chmod +x start.sh
CMD ["/start.sh"]
```

Code 11: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

route add default gw 182.168.1.2

route del default gw 182.168.1.1

#Indicate that machine will receive the flows
insmod ipt-netflow/ipt_NETFLOW.ko destination=182.168.1.4:2055 debug=1
```

```

iptables -P OUTPUT DROP
iptables -P FORWARD DROP

#Rules so that the traffic that reaches the machine is not duplicated

iptables -A INPUT -i eth0 -p tcp --dport 22 -m state --state NEW,
↳ ESTABLISHED -j ACCEPT
iptables -A OUTPUT -o eth0 -p tcp --sport 22 -d 182.168.1.2 -m state --
↳ state ESTABLISHED -j ACCEPT

iptables -A OUTPUT -o eth0 -p tcp --dport 22 -d 182.168.1.2 -m state --
↳ state NEW,ESTABLISHED -j ACCEPT
iptables -A INPUT -i eth0 -p tcp --sport 22 -m state --state ESTABLISHED
↳ -j ACCEPT

#We redirect the traffic to the netflow module, to generate the flows
iptables -I FORWARD -j NETFLOW
iptables -I INPUT -j NETFLOW
iptables -I OUTPUT -j NETFLOW

#Launch cron to generate CIC flows
cron && tail -f /var/log/cron.log &

/etc/init.d/ssh start

tcpdump -i eth0 -C 1 -w '/home/tcpdump-capture/capture.pcap'

/bin/bash

```

The file in charge of saving network traffic in PCAP format that the machine receives is **get-data.sh**.

Code 12: get-data.sh

```

#!/bin/bash

var=$(cat /checkNetflow.txt)
if [ $var -eq 1 ]; then
    #transform the flows saved in the router into a single pcap
    mergecap /home/tcpdump-capture/* -w /home/total-traffic/merged.
    ↳ pcap

    #Inform the attacker that we have finished saving the data
    sshpass -p "password" ssh -o StrictHostKeyChecking=no root@182
    ↳ .168.1.2 "echo 2 > /checkRouterNetflow.txt"

fi

```

Dockerfile netflow_warehouse

In the receiver we will have to install **iptables** to open port 2055 where the traffic will be received. In addition, we will have to install **flow-tools**, create a folder to receive the flows and indicate this folder in the configuration file **flow-capture.conf**. Finally, we will launch the service so that it captures the flows in the file `bf_start.sh` and we will execute a task in cron that is pending to receive the signal from the *router* to export the streams to CSV and save them to the *host*.

Code 13: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04

#Install the necessary packages
RUN apt-get -y update
RUN apt-get -y install apt-utils
RUN apt-get -y install net-tools
RUN apt-get install -y iputils-ping traceroute nano
RUN apt-get install iptables -y

#Install and configure the Flow-tools tool to save Netflow traffic
RUN apt-get -y install flow-tools
RUN apt-get -y install cron
ADD flow-capture.conf /etc/flow-tools/flow-capture.conf
RUN mkdir /var/log/flow
RUN mkdir /home/netflow_flows

#Install the ssh server
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y openssh-server
RUN apt-get install sshpass
RUN mkdir /var/run/sshd
RUN echo 'root:password' | chpasswd
RUN sed -i 's/#PermitRootLogin prohibit-password/PermitRootLogin yes/' /
    ↪ etc/ssh/sshd_config

# SSH login fix. Otherwise user is kicked off after login
RUN sed 's@session\s*required\s*pam_loginuid.so@session optional
    ↪ pam_loginuid.so@g' -i /etc/pam.d/sshd
ENV NOTVISIBLE "in users profile"
RUN echo "export VISIBLE=now" >> /etc/profile
EXPOSE 22

#File to check that the receiver has finished
RUN echo 0 > checkReceiver.txt

#Copy the script to generate the flows
COPY getNetflow.sh .
COPY checkFlows.sh .
```



```
COPY netflow-cron /etc/cron.d/netflow-cron
RUN chmod 0644 /etc/cron.d/netflow-cron
RUN crontab /etc/cron.d/netflow-cron
RUN touch /var/log/cron.log
RUN chmod +x getNetflow.sh
RUN chmod +x checkFlows.sh

#Launch start.sh
COPY start.sh .
RUN chmod +x start.sh
CMD ["/start.sh"]
```

Code 14: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

#We establish that the Gateway is the router and not the host
route add default gw 182.168.1.2

route del default gw 182.168.1.1

service flow-capture start

#Open the port that NetFlow will receive
iptables -A INPUT -p udp --dport 2055 -j ACCEPT

cron && tail -f /var/log/cron.log &

/etc/init.d/ssh start

/bin/bash
```

The file in charge of being aware of receiving the signal from the *router* and exporting the flows is the one named **getNetflow.sh**.

Code 15: getNetflow.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

var=$(cat /checkReceiver.txt)

if [ $var -eq 1 ]; then
    #We transform the flows stored in the router into a single csv

    sleep 120
```

```
flow-cat /var/log/flow/* | flow-export -f2 > /home/netflow_flows/  
  ↪ netflow_flows.csv  
  
#We tell the router that it's done  
sshpass -p "password" ssh -o StrictHostKeyChecking=no root@182  
  ↪ .168.1.2 "echo 2 > /checkRouter.txt"  
  
fi
```

Code 16: flow-capture.conf

```
-w /var/log/flow -n 900 0/182.168.1.1/2055
```

Code 17: netflow-cron

```
* * * * * root /getNetflow.sh  
*/10 * * * * root /checkFlows.sh
```

Dockerfile generator

The generator is in charge of launching the project with the *scripts* to produce web, *mail* and SSH traffic. As soon as it is launched, the container automatically starts generating traffic thanks to the script **start.sh**.

Code 18: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04  
  
#Install the necessary packages  
RUN apt-get update  
RUN apt-get install -y net-tools  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y iputils-ping traceroute nano  
  ↪ wget  
  
#We install the dependencies to execute the project  
RUN apt-get install -y openssh-client  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y firefox  
RUN apt-get install -y psmisc  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y python-pip  
RUN apt-get -y install cron  
COPY netflow-cron /etc/cron.d/netflow-cron  
RUN chmod 0644 /etc/cron.d/netflow-cron  
RUN crontab /etc/cron.d/netflow-cron  
RUN touch /var/log/cron.log  
RUN pip install paramiko selenium xvfbwrapper  
RUN apt-get install -y xvfb  
RUN wget https://github.com/mozilla/geckodriver/releases/download/v0  
  ↪ .26.0/geckodriver-v0.26.0-linux64.tar.gz  
RUN tar -xzvf geckodriver-v0.26.0-linux64.tar.gz
```

```
RUN mv geckodriver /opt/  
RUN mkdir generate-traffic  
COPY generate-traffic/ ./generate-traffic/  
RUN chmod +x ./generate-traffic/start_generate_traffic.sh  
  
#Launch start.sh  
COPY start.sh .  
RUN chmod +x start.sh  
CMD ["/start.sh"]
```

Code 19: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash  
  
#We establish that the Gateway is the router and not the host.  
route add default gw 182.168.1.2  
  
route del default gw 182.168.1.1  
  
cron && tail -f /var/log/cron.log &  
  
#We launch the scripts to generate the traffic  
  
./generate-traffic/start_generate_traffic.sh 2> /dev/null  
  
/bin/bash
```

SSH Dockerfile

This container is in charge of raising an SSH service to which the generator will connect to generate SSH traffic.

Code 20: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:16.04  
  
#Install SSH  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y openssh-server  
RUN mkdir /var/run/sshd  
RUN echo 'root:password' | chpasswd  
RUN sed -i 's/PermitRootLogin prohibit-password/PermitRootLogin yes/' /  
    ↪ etc/ssh/sshd_config  
  
# SSH login fix. Otherwise user is kicked off after login  
RUN sed 's@session\s*required\s*pam_loginuid.so@session optional  
    ↪ pam_loginuid.so@g' -i /etc/pam.d/sshd  
ENV NOTVISIBLE "in users profile"  
RUN echo "export VISIBLE=now" >> /etc/profile  
EXPOSE 22
```

```
CMD ["/usr/sbin/sshd", "-D"]
```

Code 21: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

#We establish that the Gateway is the router and not the host, in this
  ↪ way all packets will go through our container that generates
  ↪ netflow
route add default gw 126.52.30.2

route del default gw 126.52.30.1

/bin/bash
```

Lab 2 - Docker

The same lab has been created to generate port scan traffic, also using Docker Compose, making the infrastructure also exportable and lighter to mount.

In the file **docker-compose.yml** we define the machines and networks that we are using. On the one hand, we define the network for the attackers to connect to one of the *router* interfaces and, on the other hand, the network to store the flows and for the attacked machines. The resulting folder structure is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Laboratory structure 2.

Both the **router**, the **netflow_generator** and the **netflow_warehouse** are the same for both the attack laboratory and the normal traffic generation laboratory.

Code 22: docker-compose.yml

```
version: "2.2"

services:
  rabbit:
    hostname: rabbit
    image: rabbitmq:latest
```



```
environment:
  - RABBITMQ_DEFAULT_USER=admin
  - RABBITMQ_DEFAULT_PASS=mypass
networks:
  - attacknet
ports:
  - "5672:5672"
depends_on:
  - router

attacker:
  image: lab/attacker
  build: ./attacker
  networks:
    - attacknet
  volumes:
    - ./attacks:/attacks/
  links:
    - rabbit
  depends_on:
    - rabbit
    - router
    - slave
  privileged: true
  tty: true

launcher:
  image: lab/launcher
  build: ./launcher
  container_name: launcher
  networks:
    attacknet:
      ipv4_address: 140.30.20.254
  volumes:
    - ./attacks:/attacks/
  links:
    - rabbit
  depends_on:
    - rabbit
    - router
    - attacker
    - netflow_generator
  privileged: true
  tty: true

netflow_warehouse:
  image: lab/netflow_warehouse
```



```
build: ./netflow_warehouse
container_name: netflow_warehouse
volumes:
  - ./results/Netflow_flows:/home/netflow_flows
networks:
  internalnet:
    ipv4_address: 152.148.48.4
depends_on:
  - router
privileged: true
tty: true

router:
  container_name: router
  build: ./router
  image: lab/router
  volumes:
    - ./results/Network_traffic:/home/total-traffic/
    - ./results/CICFlows:/home/total-cic/
  networks:
    attacknet:
      ipv4_address: 140.30.20.2
    internalnet:
      ipv4_address: 152.148.48.2
  privileged: true
  tty: true

netflow_generator:
  container_name: netflow_generator
  build: ./netflow_generator
  image: lab/netflow_generator
  volumes:
    - ./results/NetflowMachineResults:/home/total-traffic/
  networks:
    internalnet:
      ipv4_address: 152.148.48.3
  privileged: true
  tty: true

slave:
  build: ./slave
  image: lab/slave
  depends_on:
    - router
    - netflow_warehouse
```

```
networks:  
  - internalnet  
privileged: true  
tty: true
```

```
networks:  
  attacknet:  
    driver: bridge  
  ipam:  
    config:  
      - subnet: 140.30.20.0/24  
        gateway: 140.30.20.1  
  
  internalnet:  
    driver: bridge  
  ipam:  
    config:  
      - subnet: 152.148.48.0/24  
        gateway: 152.148.48.1
```

Attacker Dockerfile

The attacker's Dockerfile contains only what is necessary to run nmap from Python. Also, in the file **start.sh**, we modify the *gateway* of the machine to be the container **router** that we have created.

Code 23: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04  
  
#Install the necessary packages  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y python3.6  
RUN apt-get install -y net-tools  
RUN apt-get install -y iputils-ping traceroute nano tcpdump  
RUN apt-get install -y python3-pip  
RUN apt-get install -y python3-nmap  
RUN pip3 install pexpect  
RUN pip3 install python3-nmap  
RUN pip3 install celery  
RUN pip3 install future  
RUN apt-get install -y psmisc  
  
#Install ssh server and config  
RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y openssh-server  
RUN apt-get install sshpass  
RUN mkdir /var/run/sshd  
RUN echo 'root:password' | chpasswd
```

```
RUN sed -i 's/#PermitRootLogin prohibit-password/PermitRootLogin yes/' /
↳ etc/ssh/sshd_config

# SSH login fix. Otherwise user is kicked off after login
RUN sed 's@session\s*required\s*pam_loginuid.so@session optional
↳ pam_loginuid.so@g' -i /etc/pam.d/sshd
ENV NOTVISIBLE "in users profile"
RUN echo "export VISIBLE=now" >> /etc/profile
EXPOSE 22

#Create the files with which we will check if the results have already
↳ been stored
RUN echo 0 > checkAttackerReceiver.txt
RUN echo 0 > checkAttackerRouter.txt
RUN echo 0 > checkAttackerNetflow.txt

#Launch start.sh
COPY start.sh .
RUN chmod +x start.sh
CMD ["/start.sh"]
```

Code 24: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

#Establish that the Gateway is the router and not the host, in this way
↳ all packets will go through our container that generates netflow
route add default gw 140.30.20.2

route del default gw 140.30.20.1

export LC_ALL=C.UTF-8
export LANG=C.UTF-8

/etc/init.d/ssh start &
```

Slave Dockerfile

This machine will only be attacked and therefore the only thing to note is that we changed its *gateway* to act as our *router* container and not the *host*.

Code 25: Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04

#Install the necessary packages
RUN apt-get update
RUN apt-get install -y net-tools
RUN apt-get install -y iputils-ping traceroute nano

#Launch start.sh
COPY start.sh .
RUN chmod +x start.sh
CMD ["/start.sh"]
```

Code 26: start.sh

```
#!/bin/bash

#Establish that the Gateway is the router and not the host, in this way
↔ all packets will go through our container that generates netflow
route add default gw 152.148.48.2

route del default gw 152.148.48.1

/bin/bash
```

Lab 2 - Distributed Attacks

In the previous version of the lab, all attacks were generated from the same machine and the IP address of that machine was modified to make it appear that the attacks were being carried out from a different set of machines. Although it fulfilled its objective, when collecting data there are parameters that could not be altered, such as the *timestamp*.

For this reason, a system has been implemented that distributes the same attack *script* among various attackers thanks to the use of a queue. This system is more effective and realistic than the previous one, but also more complex when it comes to a user being able to create their own *scripts*, since they have to develop them taking into account how its distribution works. In order for attacks to be launched automatically without repeating them, a machine has been implemented that is responsible for adding the tasks of the attack *script* to the queue so that the attackers can simply execute those tasks. In this way the execution is automated and its complexity is reduced, thus obtaining a simple scheme as shown in figure 11.

To distribute the attacks, a library called Celery has been used. Celery connects to a previously created queue where tasks are stored. Each of the *workers* (in our case attackers) will execute them in an orderly manner. Once the attack tasks are finished, a function will be executed to store the data and end the laboratory. **This function should be used in any newly developed script as specified in the template found on later pages.**

Figure 11: Laboratory scheme 2.

In the final structure of the laboratory, shown in figure 12, there is the **attacks** folder, which will be the only one with which the user interacts if they want to add new *scripts* to the system. This folder contains the different *scripts* necessary both to be able to add the tasks to the queue and execute them, and to establish the connection between the queue and the *workers*. This folder is automatically added as a data volume to both the attackers and the *launcher*, so that the launcher has the necessary information to connect to the queue and add the tasks, and the attackers can execute those tasks.

Figure 12: Final structure of the laboratory 2.

Celery

Inside the attacks folder, figure 13, there is the *script* **celery.py** that will be in charge of creating an object Celery and establish the connection with the queue that we have selected, specifically, a RabbitQM queue. This file **does not need to be modified to create new attack scripts**.

Figure 13: Structure of the folder “attacks” of laboratory 2.

Code 27: celery.py

```
from __future__ import absolute_import
from celery import Celery
app = Celery('attacks', broker='amqp://admin:mypass@rabbit:5672', backend=
    ↪ 'rpc://', include=['attacks.tasks'], broker_connection_max_retries
    ↪ =400, broker_pool_limit=0)
```

The first argument is the name of the current module, and the second is the URL of the broker that will be exposed on port 5672.

Basic example

The *script* **run_task.py** can be defined as a caller. This *script* will be in charge of storing the tasks in the queue so that the *workers* can execute them later. These tasks are located in the **tasks.py** file. A simple example would be the following:

```
from .tasks import suma

numeroSumas = 10
sumando1 = 0
sumando2 = 1

while numeroSumas > 0:
    suma.delay(sumando1, sumando2)
    sumando1 = sumando1 + 1
    sumando2 = sumando2 + 1
    numeroSumas = numeroSumas - 1
```

We import the sum function from the task file and create a loop that calls this function by adding different numbers. In this way, each iteration of the loop will be executed by one of the workers in a distributed way.

```
from __future__ import absolute_import
from attacks.celery import app

@app.task
```

```
def suma( sumando1, sumando2):  
    return sumando1 +sumando2
```

We import the Celery instance that we defined earlier and define the functions for our App with a decorator. This example is possibly the easiest to program with Celery.

Let's now consider the previous example with the actual attack. This *script* is the same one that we used in the attacker of the previous model but adapted to work with Celery.

run_task.py

As in the previous exercise, in this case we are going to run a loop to update the ports and the type of attack to be carried out. These parameters will be passed to the **scan_ports** function of **tasks.py** which will simply call nmap with the provided parameters. In this way, each worker in a distributed and parallel way will execute the different calls to scan_ports and, therefore, the scans.

Code 28: run_task.py

```
from .tasks import scan_ports  
from celery.result import ResultSet  
from .end_attack.end_attack import end_attack  
import subprocess as sp  
import time  
  
r = ResultSet([])  
  
def start_ports_scanner():  
    NUMBER_OF_PORTS = 65535  
    # The port range sets the number of ports in a block that each  
    ↪ attacker has to scan (so it must be a divisor of NUMBER_OF_PORTS  
    ↪ ).  
    port_range = 771  
    initial_port = 1  
    final_port = port_range  
    # List of specific scan types for the tool nmap.  
    scan_type = ['-sU', '-sO', '-sM', '-sN', '-sF', '-sS', '-sT', '-sA', '  
    ↪ -sW', '-sX']  
    scan_index = len(scan_type) - 1  
    global r  
    # Do each scan type for the total number of ports.  
    while final_port < NUMBER_OF_PORTS or scan_index != 0:  
        r.add(scan_ports.delay(initial_port, final_port, scan_type[  
            ↪ scan_index]))  
        # Next scan type or block to scan.  
        if final_port == NUMBER_OF_PORTS:  
            scan_index = scan_index - 1  
            initial_port = 1  
            final_port = port_range  
    else:
```

```
        initial_port = final_port
        final_port += port_range

def end_ports_scanner():
    global r
    r.join()
    if r.ready() == True:
        end_attack()

if __name__ == '__main__':
    start_ports_scanner()
    end_ports_scanner()
```

Once the attacks have finished, you must always call the **end_attack ()** function, which will be the same regardless of the type of attack and which will save all the data and close the laboratory. The *script end_attack* is already developed to save the data and it is not necessary to modify it.

Code 29: tasks.py

```
from __future__ import absolute_import
from attacks.celery import app
from pexpect import pxssh
import nmap
import os
import random
import subprocess as sp
import time

@app.task
def scan_ports(initial_port, final_port, scan_type):
    wait_time = random.randrange(5, 10)
    nm = nmap.PortScanner()
    results = nm.scan(random_ip(), str(initial_port) + '-' + str(
        ↪ final_port), arguments=scan_type + ' --scan-delay ' + str(
        ↪ wait_time))

def random_ip():
    # The number of slaves must be the same as in the config.yaml file.
    slaves = 200
    # The first five IPs in the slave range are already reserved.
    scope = slaves + 5
    randomize_ip = random.randrange(5, scope)
```

```
ip = "152.148.48." + str(randomize_ip)
print("IP: " + ip)
return ip
```

Integration of both types of attackers

Performing the attacks in a distributed way brings realism to the laboratory by simulating a real distributed attack. The distribution of these attacks also implies a slight increase in complexity when writing new attacks. Taking into account the previous paradigm, the attack carried out in a unique way by a machine has been integrated into the final laboratory. In this way, a user will be able to decide which option best suits their needs. To accomplish this task, the lab provides two different docker-compose files. The **docker-compose.yml** that acts by default in Docker will launch the lab with distributed attackers, while the **docker-compose-simple-attacker.yml** will run the lab with a single attacker. With the `-f` option of docker-compose we can select the file `doker-compose-attacker-single.yml` to launch the non-distributed attack.